

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

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List of Abbreviations

CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
DGM	Dynamic Graph Modeller
APM	Application Programming Model
ZTP	Zero Touch Provisioning
WPs	Work Packages
UC	Use Case
GNNs	Graph Neural Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SDK	Software Development Kit
AC	Application Controller
DOA	Description of Action
IS	Innovative Solutions
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
VTE	Virtual Training Environment
FL	Federated Learning

DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
UI	User Interface
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
GUI	Graphical User Interface
TDC	Telemetry Data Collector
SRM	Security Risk Modeller
XAI	Explainable AI
IP	Intellectual Property
ECA	Eclipse Contributor Agreement
QoS	Quality of Service
DTU	Digital Twin Utilizer

1. Executive Summary

ENACT's vision is the development and deployment of an advanced hyper-distributed platform that seamlessly integrates cloud, edge, and physical resources. This platform is designed to support dynamic, data-intensive applications by leveraging cutting-edge AI-driven orchestration, robust data management, and secure communication mechanisms. The primary goal is to optimize resource utilisation and enhance the performance of distributed applications across diverse environments.

Deliverable D2.3, " ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum (CCC) Reference Architecture", presents the first iteration of the architecture of the ENACT platform, gives a detailed description of its layers and an overview of the platform's components and their interactions. The proposed innovations and technological advancements are also highlighted, showcasing the core enablers of the ENACT platform, among them the Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) of the CCC, a Cognitive Orchestrator for resource and application adaptations, and an Application Programming Model (APM) to develop and deploy hyper-distributed applications.

The ENACT platform's multi-layer architecture integrates functionalities that create a cohesive, scalable, infrastructure that allows for secure and interoperable data sharing. The modular design supports future extensions and allows for the individual use and exploitation of platform components. This deliverable also provides workflows that illustrate core functionalities such as for Deployment and Training of AI models and the interactions and data exchanges between the core components and services of the ENACT platform that ensure efficient operation and management. Additionally, through its Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP) capabilities these interactions take place with heterogeneous edge and cloud resources with minimal manual intervention.

Through the aforementioned APM, the architecture also supports novel application development that equips applications with essential AI and services for communication, continuous monitoring and self-optimisation. The ENACT Application Programming Model enables the development of applications optimized for dynamic deployment and execution within the compute continuum, enhancing their performance and adaptability.

This document serves as a guideline for the project's ongoing research and development activities (M1-M18), ensuring alignment with the specified components and interfaces, continuous improvement and final release. It is intended to support the technical work packages (WPs) and the development, evaluation, and integration activities of the project's use cases. By providing such a comprehensive framework, the ENACT platform's architecture ensures the project's ambition to deliver a robust, scalable, and secure platform for modern data-driven applications.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The deliverable focuses on defining the reference architecture of the ENACT platform for an integrated CCC built upon the outcomes of predominantly Task 2.3 (Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum), but also Task 2.2 (Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum) which describes the components comprising the ENACT Architecture.

This deliverable (D2.3) presents the first outcomes of Task 2.3 – “ENACT CCC Reference Architecture” and focuses on defining the reference architecture of the ENACT platform for an integrated CCC. It describes the ENACT concept for application- and infrastructure-level adaptations in the CCC and the key technological innovations contributed by Consortium partners that act as enablers of the platform towards realising its vision. In addition, it also presents the high-level design of the overall ENACT architecture and the definition and interactions of its layers and components. The document also describes the three (3) main functions of the proposed architecture, i.e. (i) deployment, (ii) training, and (iii) inference via the relevant workflows. Finally, this deliverable highlights the cognitive capabilities of the secure, adaptive and distributed ENACT platform in supporting highly-demanding, dynamic and safety-critical applications in the context of the two high impact use cases (UCs) across different domains with heterogeneous needs.

The deliverable is produced within WP2 (“Requirements and Specifications for CCC”), and the work presented was completed within T2.3 (“Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum”); During the completion of this work, there was close collaboration with T2.2 (“Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum”) which describes the platform’s key building blocks, and the associated interfaces comprising the ENACT Architecture in a highly iterative process between the two Tasks.

In the next period, ENACT enters the second iteration of the implementation towards the final architecture design (M9–M18). To this end, D2.3 will serve as a guideline for the remaining research and development activity conducted in the technical work packages (WP4–WP6). The technical work packages will have to ensure that project’s developments are fully aligned with the specifications of the final architecture and interfaces.

2.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 (Executive Summary):** Provides a summary of the most relevant parts of the project in relation to this deliverable.
- **Section 2 (Introduction):** Provides an introduction to this deliverable, which includes the purpose and scope, Relation to other WP’s and Tasks, and the Structure of the deliverable.
- **Section 3 (The ENACT Concept and Approach):** Provides an overview of the ENACT platform’s vision, goals and how these are planned to be achieved through the proposed architecture.
- **Section 4 (Innovations Enabling the ENACT Architecture):** Provides an overview of the innovative solutions that the consortium partners bring to the project and that will act as key enablers for realising the ENACT concept.
- **Section 5 (ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Architecture):** Provides a high-level overview of the proposed architecture as well as information flow views that highlight the interactions and exchange of information between the core components and services of the ENACT platform and the steps taken to achieve its main functionalities.
- **Section 6 (ENACT Layers and Components):** Provides a detailed description of the Layers the proposed ENACT CCC architecture consists of with relevant diagrams, as well as the components of each Layer with a brief overview of their main specifications for better understanding of their functions.

- **Section 7 (Application of the ENACT Architecture in the Involved Pilots):** Provides a general description of each ENACT Pilot, describing how the proposed ENACT architecture enables the pilots' requirements and goals including which components play a pivotal role.
- **Section 8 (Conclusions):** Provides concluding remarks and closes the deliverable.

3. The ENACT Concept and Approach

ENACT develops cutting-edge techniques and technology solutions to realise a CCC that can address the needs for optimal (edge and Cloud) resource management and dynamic scaling, elasticity, and portability of hyper-distributed data-intensive applications. To achieve that, ENACT develops a set of innovative techniques and technological solutions that enable: the modelling and management of distributed resources from edge and cloud layers in the compute continuum, the dynamic deployment of distributed applications on the edge and cloud resources and adaptation of distributed applications to optimise their performance as well as resource and energy efficiency. The innovative techniques and solutions developed in the project are delivered as:

- Tools to connect and discover distributed resources, devices and services across the compute continuum, characterise and model them; to support complex application deployment and execution needs. These include techniques and tools for ZTP to support dynamic discovery and networking of edge-cloud resources and real-time visibility of distributed resources as DGM. This solution, similar to a digital twin of the edge-cloud continuum, will support AI applications by ensuring optimal execution across the Cloud, Edge, and Far-Edge levels.
- AI-powered orchestrator, capable of deploying and managing applications across distributed (edge and cloud) nodes in an optimal way to support the energy efficiency and adaptations in distributed applications. The AI-powered edge-to-cloud orchestrator will use GNNs and Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques to compute the most suitable deployment configurations for the distributed applications. This orchestrator will leverage real-time data from edge-cloud resource models and other factors (e.g., security and optimisation policies) to manage edge-cloud resources and workloads, optimising both application performance and underlying infrastructure. The AI-powered scheduler will continuously learn from deployment decisions, application behaviour, and infrastructure performance, improving its decision-making over time. It will also adapt to threats like performance degradation, device churn, communication issues, and the integration of new devices or partners.
- Application development toolkit for developing or adapting complex applications; making them distributed, robust and adaptive in order to optimise their performance and take advantage of the resources in the CCC. The application development toolkit will include an ENACT APM that provides, encompassing non-intrusive sidecar libraries, mechanisms to secure, self-register, model, identify, synchronise, communicate, continuously monitor, and autonomously operate hyper-distributed applications. The APM will enable the development of intelligent and adaptive applications, which can take various factors (such as performance and energy efficiency) into account to optimise their own operational behaviour. Based on the functions and components prescribed in the APM, the intelligent and adaptive applications will also be able to work with the AI-powered orchestrator to dynamically reconfigure their deployment configurations. In this respect, the APM will support specifications of intelligent and adaptive applications that are optimised for cloud, edge and far-edge deployment and its implementation will be supported by a Software Development Kit (SDK).

With the above innovations, ENACT realises adaptation at two levels in the edge-cloud continuum.

3.1 Infrastructure-Level Adaptation

The Infrastructure Level Adaptation is concerned with ensuring the optimal utilisation and management of available resources in order to ensure that applications are deployed at the most relevant resources (e.g. taking into account their location, energy consumption, cost, regulations etc) and at the same time, the resources are used in the best possible way e.g. (in terms of performance, energy consumption etc.). The infrastructure level adaptation in ENACT is realised through a combination of GNNs and RL techniques (as shown in Figure 1) to support automated and intelligent decisions concerning scheduling, orchestration and optimal deployment of distributed applications in the edge-cloud continuum.

In ENACT, GNN is used to model and analyse data concerning the distributed and diverse edge-cloud resources. The data for the resource modelling is gathered from a telemetry service (developed in the project) that is responsible for gathering data from available edge and cloud resources. Based on the availability of the telemetry data, a graph-based representation of the edge-cloud continuum is developed in the ENACT DGM component. The GNNs operate on the developed graph model to help analyse the state of the edge-cloud continuum, the evolution of connections between (edge-cloud) resources over time and the predictions about suitable deployment configurations for distributed applications. The Graph Modeller also helps with the monitoring and management of diverse and distributed infrastructure resources. The monitoring and prediction functionality of the Graph Modeller is used by an intelligent orchestrator that uses RL techniques to make decisions on the adaptive management of the edge-cloud resources and deployment of distributed applications. The adaptations enabled by the GNN and RL-based orchestrator help optimise the utilisation of the available edge-cloud resources while best serving the infrastructure/resource requirements of the distributed applications.

Figure 1: Infrastructure and Application-Level Adaptation

3.2 Application-Level Adaptation

To complement infrastructure level adaptation, the ENACT project develops techniques and tools that support adaptation at the application level. The application-level adaptation techniques support the development of intelligent and adaptive applications that are able to monitor their own behaviour and dynamically adjust their operations and deployment configurations based on their optimisation criteria e.g. performance, resource utilisation, energy efficiency etc.

In ENACT, the application-level adaptation is realised through an APM that provides the basic constructs or building blocks for developing intelligent and adaptive applications in the form of libraries and customisable functions. Application developers can use these building blocks to develop (from scratch) or enhance (existing) applications, equipping them with capabilities such as resource monitoring, performance monitoring, triggers, constraints and optimisation functions.

A key concept prescribed in the ENACT APM is the Application Controller (AC) as shown in Figure 1. Once configured, the purpose of this component is to control the execution and deployment configuration of the application based on the monitoring of application and applying its internal optimisation or adaptation criteria. Within the ENACT environment, the AC can interact with the AI Orchestrator to suggest the best suited adaptation actions, which can relate to load balancing, elasticity and energy efficiency. In turn, the AI Orchestrator can then decide which adaptation actions to implement as it has the full overview of the available infrastructure (through the GNN, as discussed in the previous section).

The implementation of the APM is supported by an SDK that provides the implementation of the software libraries, documentation and tools that developers can use to develop and enhance their applications.

3.3 ENACT Approach

The implementation approach defined in ENACT, as described in the Description of Action (DOA) consists of four (4) interrelated phases:

Phase 1: Definition of Requirements & System Architecture (WP2): The first phase (WP2) focuses on defining the specific background (state of art, market needs, technical and non-technical specifications) in which the ENACT solutions will be developed and implemented. The specifications (D2.1) and requirements of the ENACT solutions (D2.2) are already specified and published. This deliverable describes the global architecture of the ENACT solutions, along with the high-level data and control flows of different components that make up the ENACT platform ecosystem. This phase concludes at M18.

Phase 2: Development & integration (WP4-WP6): Phase 2 includes the development of the ENACT software-driven innovations and encapsulates the development of the core functionalities concerning DGM, ML-based GNN models for deployment decision support, virtual training of the GNNs, distributed storage, ZTP service, APM and cognitive orchestration for the management of applications and underlying infrastructure.

This phase has been initiated with the state of art and initial design specification of the technological solutions being investigated in WP4, WP5 and WP6 of the project. Background research and partner discussions in this early stage of the project has helped to clarify the scope of the different solutions, the technological choices and the innovation potential for all key components.

This phase concludes at M18 with the release of first prototypes of the technological solutions from WP4 and WP5. The work on APM, SDK and application adaptation techniques continues in WP6 until the end of the project in M36.

Phase 3: UC Implementations, Evaluations and Continuous Improvements (WP3, WP7): Phase 3 focuses on the preparation of UC applications, based on the APM and other techniques developed in WP6, together with their implementations and evaluations - in WP3. In this early phase of the project, the work focused on describing the UC scenarios and specifications (in D2.2). This foundational work will be followed with further investigations of the UC scenarios and preparing the implementation for defined use-case scenarios.

The lessons learned and feedback from UC implementations and evaluation in WP3, will be used to update the technical requirements and specifications in WP7. The evaluations of the UC implementations will be carried out with the involvement of all technological and user partners - to focus not only on the technological assessments but also the human-centricity, and socio-technical impact in the wider context of the project and UC domains.

Figure 2: ENACT WP Structure

All above phases are supported by horizontal activities (Phase 4), namely project management in WP1 and communication, dissemination and exploitation in WP8. The horizontal activities have started with the initiation of the project, involving stakeholder engagement, collaborations with relevant initiatives and knowledge exchange with the scientific community and industry.

4. Innovations Enabling the ENACT Architecture

The ENACT platform is enabled by a set of innovative solutions (IS) that have been previously explored and are presently at early Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 2-3 by consortium members. Building upon this foundation, these innovations will undergo further development, testing, and demonstration throughout the project, aiming to reach TRL 5 by its conclusion. Each innovation is scheduled for pilot site demonstration, ensuring practical validation and application. These solutions are integral to all ENACT UCs, serving as essential enablers for realizing the CCC and driving forward

the project's objectives in optimizing resource management and data processing across edge and cloud environments.

4.1 Dynamic Graph Modeller

The DGM provides a comprehensive visualisation of the ENACT continuum, offering a rich and intuitive representation of the nodes and edges that define it. This is a visualisation tool that obtains data from the different deployments within the ENACT (edge-cloud) environment and converts them into a graph format, while displaying their respective edges and nodes.

Besides representing those deployments in a visual way, users could also edit those graphs or these graphs can be used by other tools and components for identifying better deployment configurations or optimisation of existing deployment configurations (e.g. achieving lower latency or better power efficiency), contributing to the overall optimisation of the continuum. For identifying the optimal deployment configurations or optimizing the existing application deployment configurations, the DGM provides graph data to the AI layer where different AI techniques/components are designed to serve that purpose. By having a tool like DGM in the ENACT Architecture it is possible to facilitate both the user and AI to view and modify the application deployments that are currently running in the ENACT environment.

Additionally, the DGM tool will feature a dedicated view for deployment risk assessment. This view will allow users to analyze potential cybersecurity and compliance risks associated with different application deployments, providing insights into vulnerabilities, potential points of failure, and other critical factors.

4.2 Graph Neural Network (GNN) Models

The ENACT GNN Models, developed using ML-based GNN algorithms, will aim for a dynamic optimisation of hyper-distributed applications. By leveraging graph representation, the models enable a more efficient and effective analysis of relationships between diverse nodes (representing edge and cloud resources). The GNN techniques are developed to proficiently model the connections among various nodes and the applications services running on them, and accurately predict optimal deployment configurations to improve application or service availability, latency, and other performance metrics.

A notable innovation in ENACT's architecture is the integration of GNNs with Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). This combination allows for sophisticated routing and deployment optimisation and the ability to generalize over previously unseen, arbitrary (edge-cloud) network topologies. The DRL+GNN architecture provides significant advantages over traditional state-of-the-art DRL algorithms, particularly in its strong generalisation capabilities and outstanding performance in networks that were not part of the training data.

More precisely, in the ENACT architecture the GNN will work alongside the AI Forecaster component, which will provide the first sub-optimal deployment configurations and schedules based on the AI forecasting techniques so that the GNN receives these configurations and schedules and can refine them to execute the necessary optimisations. The use of GNN, alongside with the other AI related components will help to maintain good adaptability and robustness in variable edge-cloud environments.

4.3 Virtual Training Environment for GNNs

ENACT introduces a Virtual Training Environment (VTE) designed to facilitate the training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models before they are deployed in the actual environment. This innovative tool also provides the opportunity to workbench the AI models, and empower users who may lack expertise in Data Analytics, Data Science, and AI techniques to train and validate their own AI/ML algorithms. The VTE is equipped with a Model Manager Module, offering a diverse array of pre-existing AI and ML algorithms ready for use. Additionally, it supports the integration of new algorithms, providing flexibility and adaptability in model training.

The VTE's Execution Environment module leverages Kubernetes pods and Docker containers to facilitate the seamless execution of model training processes. This ensures that the training environment is both scalable and efficient, catering to the dynamic needs of users. Furthermore, the VTE includes a Federated Learning (FL) module, enabling models to be trained in a distributed manner across the CCC. This approach enhances the robustness and generalizability of the trained models by leveraging diverse data sources.

To support the efficient and dynamic usage of the tool, the VTE offers a range of additional functionalities. These include a user-friendly graphical interface, robust security measures, and comprehensive user management features. By extending an existing analytics workbench, ENACT will enhance the VTE's capabilities to support the training of GNN models, thereby realizing the full potential of the ENACT architecture. This holistic approach ensures that users can effectively harness the power of AI and ML, regardless of their technical background.

4.4 Cognitive Scheduler for Edge-Cloud Continuum

ENACT introduces an AI-powered scheduler that will enable enhanced decision-making in the deployment and orchestration of applications, as well as optimal task allocation and dynamic resource management across the computing continuum.

The scheduler's advanced functionality is achieved through the combined execution of AI-enabled forecasting mechanisms together with the GNN and DRL techniques. More specifically, AI forecasting algorithms are employed to generate predictions on near-future network status and application performance and suggest sub-optimal resource configurations and task allocation plans. These sub-optimal schedules are fed to GNNs to be refined based on information about node availability and evolving interconnections in the ENACT edge-cloud continuum represented by dynamic graphs, as well as on real-time telemetry data as acquired by ENACT's Telemetry Data Collector (TDC). Finally, the GNNs-updated schedules are inputted to a dedicated DRL agent which is responsible for optimizing the scheduling considering both application requirements and network and infrastructure status.

Overall, this multistage scheduling optimisation process integrates pertinent AI models to harness the power of AI in each of its steps to progressively refine the scheduling plans, eventually resulting in the optimal solution. This process is used by the ENACT's intelligent scheduler to dynamically adapt the running applications and services to changing network and infrastructure conditions across the computing continuum, such as varying workloads, network congestion and node failures.

4.5 Application Programming Model

The APM is designed to facilitate the development and deployment of the intelligent and responsive applications that are able to take advantage of the dynamic resource allocation and scheduling (supported by the Cognitive Scheduler) in ENACT. The APM layer provides a structured approach that allows intelligent distributed applications to be programmed via the SDK. This way, the complexities of underlying systems are abstracted thus allowing developers to focus on business logic. The APM also supports a type of model-driven development, enabling developers to design applications using high-level models/templates. This model promotes the reusability, maintainability, and scalability of applications across the edge-cloud continuum.

The APM is offered as a set of software libraries representing programmatic behaviour simulators that can be incorporated in different applications or can be used through APIs.

Specifically, the initial implementation of the APM is based on the following roadmap:

1. Implementation of libraries with simple individual embedded behaviour simulators.
2. Implementation of API (CRUD) accessible by the SDK (at this point, basic integrations tests can already be performed).
3. Expansion of the behaviour simulators to test user experience when using the SDK and detect potential issues early.

The libraries will initially be deployed on an easy to reach host, prioritizing ease of access from the developers (or the ENACT SDK) and facilitating early integration tests. Meanwhile, investigations on potential issues with deployment within a Kubernetes environment are performed so that scalability for the usage of the APM is achieved.

To ensure reliability of the APM usage and early detection of potential issues that increase exponentially in severity and cause ambiguity later in the development stages as well as during normal operation, the APM will contain a self-governed and powered metric report and acquisition layer.

All APM libraries will natively allow reporting of metrics and logs to a dedicated ENACT platform component, that will handle storage and distribution. The APM will contain a dedicated library that allows the interaction (CRUD) with the APM meta metrics component (the meta metrics library will also report usage metrics).

Using the APM meta metric library, a maintenance/support technician, or a power user can consume APM usage data, in a similar fashion to the metric data from other ENACT platform components (retrieved through the APM).

4.6 Software Development Kit

The ENACT SDK is a toolkit that provides developers with the necessary tools, libraries, and documentation to create, test, and deploy applications within the ENACT ecosystem. The SDK includes application programming interfaces (APIs) for accessing APM libraries, ENACT services, debugging tools, and integration capabilities with various development environments. It supports multiple programming languages and frameworks, ensuring flexibility and ease of use for developers. The SDK also includes sample user interface (UI) applications and templates to help developers get started quickly and efficiently.

The SDK will serve as an interface to the APM, utilizing the abstraction provided by it to the different ENACT components. This integration simplifies access to core functionalities, empowering developers to efficiently initiate, build, and scale their applications and codebases. By leveraging these advanced abstractions, the SDK enhances development workflows, reducing complexity and enabling faster iteration on scalable solutions.

4.7 ENACT Zero-Touch Provisioning Services

ZTP services in ENACT will help at managing the discovery and configuration of devices and applications across the edge-cloud continuum. ZTP eliminates the need for manual intervention, reducing the time and effort required for dynamic provisioning of resources to the distributed applications and services. It ensures that devices are configured consistently and securely, enabling rapid scaling and deployment of applications and services. ZTP leverages policies and automation scripts to provision devices automatically as they are added to the network, ensuring seamless integration and operation.

The ZTP services developed in ENACT will support the configuration of both bare metal devices and virtual machines, depending on the specific requirements. This process begins with the installation of the operating system and continues through the setup of necessary ENACT components and additional applications required to transform a device into a fully functional ENACT cluster.

Additionally, the ZTP services will communicate with the Orchestrator to provide updates on machines that have already been deployed, as well as those that are ready and awaiting integration into the ENACT cluster. This allows the Orchestrator to instruct the ZTP services on how to scale the infrastructure up or down based on demand, ensuring an efficient environment for deploying scalable applications.

4.8 Edge-Cloud Networking Techniques

The Cognitive Orchestrator will enable the vision of the ENACT platform through three necessary innovations. The first innovation is the capability to schedule processes in co-operation with other components in the ENACT platform. This Intelligent Decision-Making Process depends on the Orchestrator's ability to receive external instructions from the other components to guide the implementation of optimal deployment plans for all ENACT applications across all ENACT managed clusters.

A second innovation ensures that deployment of the applications and services remains optimal over time. This requires continuous monitoring of the status of the clusters to detect performance issues with regards to the running applications and clusters or other kind of problems like node/network failures. Feedback from running applications will also be continuously monitored to understand when current deployments do not allow applications to comply with their specific requirements. When faced with those dynamic changes, the ENACT Cognitive Orchestrator can trigger some changes in the current deployment or request new deployment plans from the applications, ensuring a dynamic and adaptable system for multiple scenarios.

The Edge-Cloud technologies used in the cluster and the technical specifications required to deploy applications on different types of devices need to be abstracted, so that the ENACT components can express the deployment plans and any deployment configuration using a deployment technology agnostic language. No matter the technological environment on an ENACT cluster, the ENACT

Cognitive Orchestrator needs to express the specification provided by other ENACT components to the targeted deployment technologies.

4.9 ENACT CCC Data Space

ENACT aims to provide a bespoke CCC Data space acting as a distributed data store that allows for large-scale storage for various components in the ENACT system. The ENACT CCC Data Space will be used mainly for storing historical telemetry data, but also datasets for AI training, in a distributed manner. This approach provides various benefits including improved data availability and content delivery times, controlled sharing of information belonging to different data owners while ensuring fine-grained access control and usage across multiple components (e.g. AI Forecaster, GNN and DRL agent), as well as data governance and sovereignty. The ENACT CCC Data Space will be built upon the Eclipse Dataspace Connector¹, an open-source connector that complies with the Data Space Connector concept and the standards introduced by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and Gaia-X; two leading initiatives in this regard.

Innovation brought by ENACT will be twofold: On the one hand, the ENACT Data Space will be tailored to the CCC model. Therefore, ENACT's distributed CCC Data Space will provide data-driven insights to assist in informed orchestration and application management decisions and enable distributed learning, while offering explicit advantages, such as data locality and reduced access times. This constitutes a novel direction that has been barely explored by academia and industry.

On the other hand, the ENACT CCC Data Space aspires to advance beyond state-of-the-art approaches by supporting object sharing, as well. Hence, ENACT endeavours to create also an object space which is expected to foster interoperability among applications, ultimately contributing to faster and enhanced application deployment and configuration.

5. ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Architecture

5.1 High-level architecture design

The proposed architecture of the ENACT platform is designed to achieve the overall ENACT vision by facilitating the dynamic and adaptive management of hyper-distributed applications across the CCC, as well as seamlessly coordinating and optimising cloud, edge, and physical resources, and ensuring efficient data processing and management across diverse environments.

The ENACT architecture is realised through a structured framework of five (5) layers and seventeen (17) components that interact vertically and horizontally, each designed to address specific aspects of resource management, data handling, application development, and security. By integrating these elements in a cohesive manner, and enhanced by FL techniques, the ENACT architecture provides a robust, scalable, and secure platform for managing data-intensive applications, optimizing resource utilisation, and enhancing the performance of distributed applications across diverse environments.

The specific roles and functionalities of the layers and components are described in Section 6 of this document. The proposed layered architecture with all components and exchanged data, is depicted in Figure 3.

¹ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

Figure 3: ENACT High-level Architecture Diagram

5.2 Information Flow Views

This section complements the description of the ENACT architecture by providing a set of information flow views that highlight the interactions and exchange of information between the core components and services of the ENACT platform and the steps taken to achieve its main functionalities. In order to highlight these functionalities, the interactions are organised into three main control flow phases that correspond to the adopted application lifecycle:

1. Deployment
2. Inference
3. Training

5.2.1 Deployment

In the context of the ENACT platform, the deployment view is essential for comprehending the effective operation of the platform, particularly in relation to optimally deploying hyper-distributed applications based on availability and infrastructures and application requirements.

5.2.1.1 Deployment Sequence Diagram (ICE)

The deployment process in the ENACT ecosystem is initiated when a user submits a request to the Orchestrator for the deployment of an application on the CCC, and within its defined constraints (such as performance, resource utilisation, energy efficiency etc). Following the request for deployment, the Orchestrator will then send a request to the AI Forecaster for an optimised schedule and deployment configuration. At this point, both the TDC, and the ZTP Service will have run in a

continuous manner to collect data around resource availability and current deployments. The TDC stores its data in the Data Manager through the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, while the ZTP service provides its data directly to the Orchestrator.

The AI forecaster, based on this data will then generate a set of sub-optimal deployment configurations and schedules for a given application and forward these to the DRL Agent. The DRL agent will then send the sub-optimal schedules to the GNN which will provide inference data. Based on the GNN inference, the DRL agent will determine the optimal configuration and pass this to the AI Forecaster, which will then request a risk assessment from the Security Risk Modeller (SRM), while also forwarding this to the DGM component so that the dynamic graph (of resources and applications) can be updated. The AI Forecaster will then select and send the optimal deployment configuration and schedule for the given application back to the orchestrator. In parallel, the DRL Agent will call the VTE to ensure check if the training data for AI models is up to date, and if not, then then the VTE will use the TDC data to train or retrain the AI models so that the up-to-date AI models (used by AI Forecaster, DRL and GNN) are always available and used for decision support.

Based on the APM libraries and SDK used for the development/enhancement of the Application, the Orchestrator will then deploy the Application according to the optimal configuration/schedule, alongside an instance of the AC as a sidecar container. The AC will first monitor the application specific telemetry data and report this to the Orchestrator but will also hold a set of Application Policies defined by the user. Depending on the values of the application telemetry data captured, and the policy constraints, the AC will perform certain actions to ensure optimal deployment conditions are maintained. The actions supported by the AC, include enabling and disabling containers to meet energy efficiency requirements, but also the sending of requests to the Orchestrator to request for either a change of deployment location or a change to the applications allocated resources.

From this point, automated deployment of the application according to its requirements is provided with continual redeployment of the app as needed, with application data and application telemetry data continuously captured and stored in the ENACT data layer to ensure model accuracy. In addition, the Orchestrator, will provide updated graph data to the DGM, which will update visualisations displayed to the user with the latest graph data.

The deployment process described above, has been illustrated in the Deployment sequence diagram provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Deployment Sequence Diagram

To provide greater insight in the Deployment process and the deployment sequence diagram shown above, a more detailed and descriptive explanation of each step in the sequence diagram has been listed below:

- **User:** A user submits request to the Orchestrator for application deployment.
- **Orchestrator:** Orchestrator requests infrastructure telemetry data from the TDC.
- **TDC:** TDC sends infrastructure telemetry data to the Data Manager through the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces.
- **Data Manager:** Data manager provides data to the TDC through the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces.
- **TDC:** The TDC sends the infrastructure telemetry data to the Orchestrator.
- **Orchestrator:** Orchestrator requests resource data from the ZTP Service.
- **ZTP Service:** ZTP Service provides resource data to the orchestrator.
- **Data Manager:** Data Manager provides resource data to the Orchestrator through the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces.
- **Orchestrator:** Orchestrator receives request for application deployment and submits request to the DGM for deployment schedules.

- **DGM:** DGM receives request for deployment schedules and forwards the request to the AI Forecaster.
- **AI Forecaster:** AI Forecaster generates a set of sub optimal schedules and deployment configurations. AI Forecaster send sub-optimal schedules to the DRL Agent.
- **DRL Agent:** DRL sends sub-optimal schedules to GNN and requests for inference data.
- **GNN:** GNN sends inference data to DRL Agent.
- **DRL Agent:** request model training from the VTE.
- **VTE:** VTE trains model requested by DRL Agent.
- **DRL Agent:** DRL Agent send optimal schedule to the AI Forecaster.
- **AI Forecaster:** AI Forecaster requests risk assessment from the SRM.
- **SRM:** SRM provides risk assessment to the AI Forecaster.
- **SRM:** SRM provides risk assessment to the DGM.
- **AI Forecaster:** AI Forecaster sends optimal schedule to the Orchestrator.
- **Orchestrator:** Orchestrator deploys application with instance of AC.
- **AC:** AC Retrieves and Enforces Application Policies defined by the application owner.
- **AC:** AC request compliance check from AI Act Compliance Checker.
- **AC:** AC Monitors and stores application telemetry data.
- **AC:** Application Controller monitors application telemetry data and based on the application policies requests redeployment from the Orchestrator.
- **Orchestrator:** Orchestrator sends updated graph data to the DGM.
- **DGM:** DGM updates visualisation displayed to the user with the latest graph data.

5.2.1.2 Deployment Architecture

The deployment process through is depicted an architecture diagram in Figure 5 (active components during this process are depicted in blue).

Figure 5: Deployment Architecture Diagram

5.2.2 Training

In the context of the ENACT platform, the training view plays a pivotal role in refining and enhancing the inference process. This view is essential for the effective operation of the platform, particularly in relation to the inference process that drives application deployment, resource allocation, and configuration across the ENACT continuum. The training view includes the flow of information necessary for creating accurate predictive models and ensuring that the system's decision-making capabilities are continuously improved.

5.2.2.1 Training Sequence Diagram

Figure 6: Training Sequence diagram

- The process begins with the **TDC**, which gathers raw telemetry data from diverse sources such as IoT devices, edge nodes and cloud servers. This data includes critical performance metrics, system logs, and other relevant network resource information essential for training AI models. The **TDC** has a basic filtering function to eliminate noise from the data generated.
- Once collected, the telemetry data is forwarded to the Data Layer through the **Data Access & Sharing Interfaces** which provide the necessary APIs and the **Data Manager** that handles the metadata and provides authentication and authorisation services, secure data storage and access in one or more distributed Data Storage Nodes across the continuum. The **Data Manager** should authorize the **Data Access & Sharing Interfaces** to request or send data.
- The network and telemetry data are stored in the **Data Manager**.
- The network and telemetry data are sent to the **VTE**.
- The **VTE** preprocesses the training data to train and test the AI models, incorporating FL and Explainable AI (XAI) functions to enhance the training process and the security of data and to ensure transparency and robustness.
- Once trained, it is sent to the **Data Access & Sharing Interfaces** so that it stored it in the **Data Manager**

5.2.2.2 Training Architecture

The training process through an architecture diagram is depicted in Figure 7 (active components during this process are depicted in blue).

Figure 7: Training Architecture diagram

5.2.2.3 Federated Learning in the ENACT Platform

Federated Learning is a decentralized approach to ML that allows multiple devices or nodes to collaboratively train a shared model while keeping their data localised. This technique enhances data privacy by ensuring that raw data never leaves the local devices, mitigating risks associated with data breaches and enhancing compliance with data protection regulations such as the AI Act. FL also facilitates scalability and large-scale deployments by allowing model training across multiple nodes, while at the same time optimising resource utilisation and data transmission, lowering bandwidth usage and improving latency.

Federated Learning Implementation in the ENACT platform

In the ENACT platform, FL is implemented across different infrastructures (clusters), each comprising a physical, edge, and cloud layer. Data from various physical devices is collected on a cloud layer server within each cluster, where local training takes place, producing a local model for each infrastructure. The parameters of each local model are then sent to a global server – which may be part of a cluster or a separate from all clusters (see Figures 8 & 9) - which aggregates them for global training. The updated global model parameters are subsequently distributed back to each cluster, updating their local models. This continuous process ensures improved model performance while maintaining data privacy and optimizing resource utilisation across the platform.

- Platform Structure:** The ENACT platform consists of multiple clusters (infrastructures), each containing a physical layer, an edge layer, and a cloud layer.

- **Data Collection:** Each cluster collects data on one of the servers in its cloud layer.
- **Local Training:** Training is performed locally within each cluster's cloud layer, resulting in a local model for each cluster.
- **Model Aggregation:** Each cluster sends its local model parameters to a separate global server.
- **Global Training:** The global server aggregates the parameters from all local models to perform global training.
- **Model Update:** The updated global model parameters are sent back to each cluster, updating their local models.
- **Continuous Process:** This process repeats continuously to keep improving the model.

Figure 8: Federated Learning in ENACT with global training on a separate node

Figure 9: Federated Learning in ENACT with global training on a cluster's node

5.2.3 Inference

Inference constitutes an essential process of the ENACT platform and pertains to generating the optimal solution for application deployment and allocation, as well as resource configuration within the ENACT continuum. It is a multistage process that is performed using AI-enabled mechanisms aiming at scheduling optimisation.

5.2.3.1 Inference Diagram

Inference is achieved through the cooperation of three ENACT components, namely the AI Forecaster, GNNs and the DRL agent. The AI Forecaster predicts future requirements and performance and generates sub-optimal schedules which are then refined by GNNs based on real-time insights on network and telemetry data, and finally optimized and deployed by the DRL, as illustrated below.

Figure 10: Inference Process Diagram

- The **AI Forecaster** obtains the latest ENACT continuum graph data as produced by the **DGM** based on real-time network and telemetry data collected by the **TDC**.
- The **AI Forecaster** employs AI-based forecasting algorithms to predict near-future resource and application requirements and performance.
- **GNNs** retrieve and refine those sub-optimal schedules using AI models which are constantly updated in the **VTE**.
- The refined sub-optimal schedules are sent back to the **AI Forecaster** and forwarded to the **DRL** agent to be optimized and sent to the **Orchestrator** to contribute to the deployment decision-making process.

5.2.3.2 Inference Architecture

The inference process through an architecture diagram is depicted in Figure 11 (active components during this process are depicted in blue).

Legend: **Components involved in Inference**
Components not involved

Figure 11: Inference Architecture Diagram

6. ENACT Layers and Components

At the core of the ENACT architecture is a multi-layer architecture which integrates components whose functionalities create a cohesive, scalable, and borderless infrastructure. The modular design supports future extensions and allows for the individual use and exploitation of platform components. This section provides diagrams of the difference Layers and their interactions and provides a brief description of their components.

6.1 Modelling Layer

6.1.1 Overview (FDI)

The Modelling Layer creates and maintains a dynamic graph model of the entire system, capturing the interactions and states of various resources across the cloud-to-edge continuum. This layer processes and analyses data from the distributed infrastructure to learn relationships within the cloud-to-edge environment. By including the DGM, this layer provides insights into understanding the system's current state and supporting deployment decisions. Additionally, the SRM ensures the system's security by assessing the potential risks associated with various deployment configurations, considering factors such as data sensitivity, network vulnerabilities, and regulatory requirements.

The Modelling Layer interacts bidirectionally with other layers. It receives real-time updates on the status of resources and application data from the Orchestration Layer. The layer then provides graph data to the AI Layer, which uses this information to generate deployment schedules. These schedules are then fed back to the Modelling Layer for risk assessment. The layer also interacts with the UI, allowing for visual graph representation and user interaction.

Figure 12: ENACT Modelling Layer Interactions

6.1.2 Modelling Layer Key Components

6.1.2.1 Dynamic Graph Modeller

Component Name	Dynamic Graph Modeller
Intro / Overview	<p>The DGM obtains data from a deployment in the ENACT environment, processes and converts it into a visual graph (edges and nodes). In addition, users can also edit this graph or send it to other tools like GNN to modify it to be more suitable regarding features like better latency, power efficiency, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Data Requester is the entry point of data to feed the component, it gathers the info of the rest of the components and prepares it to be transferred to the Graph Modeller component. The Graph Modeller is in charge of convert the entry data into a graph structure of nodes and edges. The Graph Visualiser represents the graph data structures providing a graphical way to ENACT operators.
Component Workflow	<p>To depict the ENACT DGM workflow, a diagram has been used to represent the interaction between internal components.</p>

Interfaces

- Data Requester Interface:**
- Overview: The Data Requester is in charge of gathering (requesting) all the info from the TDC & Monitoring Engine and Orchestrator.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- Graph Modeller Interface:**
- Overview: The Graph Modeller receives the data of the system structured as a graph and represents it in a visual way.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: GEXF, GRAPHML (graph formats)
- Software as a Service
 - Docker Containers
 - Helm Chart

Deployment Type

The deployment form of the DGM will be a containerised solution in Docker that can be easily deployed in a Kubernetes environment with the use of Helm. The solution will be packaged as a Helm chart and will be ready to deploy by the Kubernetes orchestrator.

Table 1: Dynamic Graph Modeller Specification Overview

6.1.2.2 Security Risk Modeller

Component Name	Security Risk Modeller (SRM)
Intro / Overview	<p>SRM is a security risk analysis tool which uses as an input the deployment configuration from the graph modeller. The graph modeller output is transformed to a system model which maps different resources of ENACT to the asset types in accordance with ISO 27005 standard. System model now represent all the functional characteristics of the hardware and software in the deployment configuration. This system model is analysed through risk modeller which will recommend some configuration updates trying to model the human interaction with the system in line with the ISO 27005 standard. Web UI provides the main interface to the modelling environment while Keycloak manages the access to the SRM service. Data transformation function will perform the conversion of the graph data to the ISO 27005 asset types. System model development function is envisioned to auto-generate the system model based on the transformed data. Risk treatment plan function will provide risk mitigation strategies which will be displayed to the user in the graph modeller GUI and also provided to the DRL to ensure risk compliance with ISO 27005 and GDPR.</p>

Component Workflow

Interfaces

System Model Interface:

- Overview: This API will take graph data as an input from the graph modeller and return mapping of the nodes and edges information to the system model attributes in accordance with ISO 27005 standard. This data will be provided to the risk modeller to generate system model for the security risk analysis.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Risk treatment plan interface:

- Overview: This API exposes methods to export security risks to other components and display these risks in the graph modeller user interface.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

- Software
- Docker container

Table 2: Security Risk Modeller Specification Overview

6.2 AI Layer

6.2.1 Overview (FDI)

The AI Layer enhances the deployment efficiency and adaptability of distributed applications across the continuum, optimising performance, security, and energy efficiency. This layer includes advanced AI models, including DRL agents and GNN, to provide intelligent orchestration and predictive management. Furthermore, the AI Forecaster component works in conjunction with these models to predict and optimize resource allocation and application performance.

The AI Layer interacts dynamically with other layers and components of the system. It receives graph data from the Modelling Layer, which provides a representation of the cloud-to-edge continuum. It also interacts with the VTE component to perform training and improvement of its models. After this processing, the AI Layer generates optimized deployment schedules and configurations. These are then sent to the SRM within the Modelling Layer for assessment, to ensure that the proposed deployments align with security standards and compliance requirements. Finally, once the schedules

have passed the security assessment, the AI Layer forwards them to the Orchestration Layer for deployment.

Figure 13: ENACT AI Layer Interactions

6.2.2 AI Layer Key Components

6.2.2.1 AI Forecaster

Component Name	AI Forecaster
Intro / Overview	<p>This tool harnesses the power of AI algorithms to efficiently forecast network data and propose a plan to allocate computing resources across the continuum for future timesteps taking into consideration the network QoS.</p> <p>The component is composed of 3 modules:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Data Analysis module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment. 2. The AI Forecasting module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the forecasted network based on application demands, security concerns and network changes to the GNN and DRL to obtain the optimized forecasted Schedule. 3. The Data Exchange module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.
Component Workflow	

Interfaces

- Overview: Interface to exchange data with other components
- Type: e.g. REST/WebSockets
- State: Synchronous or asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

Either as a Docker container or K8S pod

Table 3: AI Forecaster Specifications Overview

6.2.2.2 Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)

Component Name	Deep Reinforcement Learning Agent
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Intro / Overview

This component harnesses the power of AI Reinforcement learning to efficiently optimize the placement of application demands to the network infrastructure.

The component is composed of 3 modules:

1. The Data analysis module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment.
2. The AI scheduling module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the optimized schedule for the application needs.
3. The Data exchange module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the DRL agent component.

Component Workflow

Interfaces

- Overview: Interface to exchange data with other components
- Type: e.g. REST/WebSockets
- State: Synchronous or asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

Either as a Docker container or K8S pod

Table 4: Deep Reinforcement Learning Specifications Overview

6.2.2.3 Graph Neural Networks (GNN)

Component Name	ENACT Graph Neural Network models
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Intro / Overview

The ENACT GNN models, developed using ML-based GNN algorithms, will permit the scheduling and dynamic optimisation of ENACT hyper-distributed applications. By leveraging graph representation, the models enable a more efficient and effective analysis of relationships between diverse nodes. They proficiently model the

connections among various services and accurately predict optimal configurations to improve service availability, latency, and other performance metrics.

Component Workflow	N/A
Interfaces	<p>Inference Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Interface provides the necessary communication between the AI Forecaster component and the GNN component in order to both receive the sub-optimal schedules that require optimisation and transfer them back to the AI Forecaster for further deployment. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Retraining Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This interface would serve to transfer the models used by the GNN to the VTE, a component that is responsible for re-training the models to make them more accurate and efficient to be used by the GNN for future optimisations. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI as a Service (AlaaS) • Docker Containers

Table 5: Graph Neural Networks Specifications Overview

6.3 Orchestration Layer

6.3.1 Overview

The Orchestration Layer orchestrates the intelligent management of resources, devices, and services within the cloud-to-edge continuum. This layer is characterised by its capability to gather real-time monitoring data from distributed resources, enabling advanced modelling and AI-driven decision-making. This allows ENACT to preserve a smart, efficient, and adaptable computing network that seamlessly integrates across edge and cloud environments.

As a communication centre for the CCC, it interfaces with Modelling, Data, and Application development layers to provide a comprehensive view of the state of the system. The main interaction is with the AI layer, where it receives optimized deployment requests, that have been assessed by the modelling layer. Accordingly, the Orchestration Layer effectively implements these deployment requests across the cloud-to-edge resources.

Legend: Components in Orchestration Layer

Components interacting with Orchestration Layer

Components not interacting with Orchestration Layer

Figure 14: ENACT Orchestration Layer Interactions

6.3.2 Orchestration Layer Key Components

6.3.2.1 Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine

Component Name	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
Intro / Overview	<p>TDC & Monitoring Engine is a set of software agents and tools utilized to monitor multi-node virtualized infrastructures. The component performs two major tasks: a) it collects computational and network metrics from multiple Kubernetes-based clusters and b) produces alerts based on certain criteria. The component consists of four modules that are responsible for collecting metrics, calculating performance indicators, producing alerts, and efficiently storing metrics to external database systems</p> <p>Infrastructure metrics include CPU and memory usage, pod and node status, network interactions between pods and infrastructure events. These metrics are collected from multiple Kubernetes clusters across the Edge-to-Cloud continuum and stored efficiently. Metrics are processed, analysed and alerts are produced when certain criteria are met (e.g. CPU usage exceeds a threshold value). TDC & Monitoring Engine is capable of forwarding alerts and metrics to registered services while also offering mechanisms to register performance indicators to be monitored</p>

Component Workflow

Interfaces
Quality Monitoring Interface:

- Overview: Exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve quality indicators and their values
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Policy Monitoring Interface:

- Overview: Exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve quality indicators and their values
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Alert Monitoring Interface:

- Overview: Exposes methods to export alerts to other components.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type Helm chart (software)

Table 6: Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine Specifications Overview

6.3.2.2 Zero Touch Provisioning (ZTP) Service

Component Name	The Zero Touch Provisioning Service
Intro / Overview	<p>The ZTP Service automates the provisioning and configuration of edge and IoT devices, ensuring they are securely onboarded to the network and managed without manual intervention.</p> <p>The ZTP Service follows a secure and automated workflow to onboard and manage devices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Device Discovery detects new devices connecting to the network • Secure Bootstrapping authenticates and securely configures devices. This can be done via Ubuntu MAAS • Configuration Management applies initial and updated configurations (DHCP). • Firmware Update Manager manages firmware updates to ensure devices are running the latest software (TFTP).

Component Workflow

Interfaces

Device Discovery API

- Overview: Detects and lists new devices
- Type: REST API
- State: Asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Secure Bootstrapping API

- Overview: Authenticates and configures devices.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Configuration Management API

- Overview: Manages device configurations.
- Type: REST API
- State: Asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Firmware Update API

- Overview: Manages and deploys firmware updates.
- Type: REST API
- State: Asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type On premises.

Table 7: Zero Touch Provisioning Service Specifications Overview

6.3.2.3 Orchestrator

Component Name	Orchestrator
Intro / Overview	<p>The Orchestrator main functions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving deployment plans from the DRL component and converting these instructions to be executed by the Orchestrator. • Monitor applications deployment over clusters. • Handle requests from the AC, with information about rescheduling plans or stopping/disabling pods. • Request new deployment plans if needed.

Component Workflow

Interfaces

- TDC Interface:**
- Overview: Interface to retrieve metric data from TDC
 - Type: MQTT
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- ZTP Interface:**
- Overview: Interface to exchange device information and configurations between Orchestrator and ZTP component
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- DRL Interface:**
- Overview: Interface to receive deployment plans from the DRL component
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- AC Interface:**
- Overview: Interface to receive optimisation requests/deployment feedback from the AC
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- Graph Modeller Interface:**
- Overview: Interface to provide information about the cluster state to the Graph Modeller
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

Docker containers.

Table 8: Orchestrator Specifications Overview

6.4 Application Development Layer

6.4.1 Overview

The Application Development Layer enables the creation of adaptive, dynamic applications that can fully leverage the diverse resources in the CCC. This layer provides tools and frameworks for developers to build applications with built-in elasticity, parallelism, load balancing, and self-optimisation characteristics.

The Application Development Layer interacts mainly with two layers across the system. By including the AC, this layer communicates with the Orchestration Layer to manage the deployment and execution of applications. It sends requests for resource allocation and receives deployment instructions, as well as general information about the system state. The AC also interacts with the Data Layer through the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces to manage storage and access to data in shared data spaces. This layer also exchanges telemetry data and access logs with the Data Layer, contributing to the overall monitoring and optimisation of the system.

Figure 15: ENACT Application Development Layer Interactions

6.4.2 Application Layer Key Components

6.4.2.1 Application Controller

Component Name	Application Controller
Intro / Overview	<p>The AC will be deployed alongside containerised components of all ENACT applications. It will monitor and collect application metrics and dynamically realise and implement application adaptation mechanisms to enable applications to modify their behaviour or configuration based on feedback from the environment or user preferences. Adaptation actions will focus on the following strategies to help optimise the application execution behaviour:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load balancing • Elasticity • Energy efficiency

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the Application Controller, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

Component Workflow:

Application Manager:

- Overview: The Application Manager provides the interface to the AC, allowing communication with the Orchestrator to support deployment and redeployment, but also the feedback of application telemetry data. This is also where the reasoning takes place to ensure that application-level policies are enforced and relevant decisions are made based on the processing of monitoring data.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Interfaces

Application Data Manager:

- Overview: The Application Data Manager facilitates the communication between deployed application components and the ENACT Data Layer.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

The AC will be deployed as a sidecar container alongside each application.

Table 9: Application Controller Specifications Overview

6.4.2.2 Application Policy Model

Component Name	Application Policy Model
Intro / Overview	Application Policy Model offers distributed application owners a means of defining runtime policies of their distributed applications, ensuring the application operates according to user runtime requirements. Policies may restrict certain deployment options in terms of computing, locality, network and storage capacity or resources availability. The Application Policy Model will define the structure and contents of Policies a distributed owner can specify and will offer a software tool to efficiently store and where other application can retrieve these policies and performs runtime optimisations.

Component Workflow

Interfaces

- Overview: Provides a user-friendly and secure way for application owners and administrators to manage runtime policies. It supports operations to create, read, update, and delete (CRUD) runtime policies.
- Type: Probably REST, though considering gRPC
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: Probably JSON

Deployment Type

Containerised Application

Table 10: Application Policy Model Specifications Overview

6.4.2.3 Application Programming Model (APM)

Component Name	Application Programming Model
Intro / Overview	<p>The APM is a framework of languages, libraries, and tools designed to build applications and services with characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, self-registering, etc. APM abstracts the complexities of building applications from scratch by providing a set of generic and reusable functions, APIs, high-level objects, and concepts for developers to create and manage distributed applications efficiently.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM Data Services offers CRUD operations through APIs for communication with data sources; • APM Dynamic Querying Layer supports querying languages functionalities for dynamic data interactions; • APM Abstraction Layer provides high-level objects and concepts to simplify application development;
Component Workflow	<pre> graph LR DI[Developer interface SDK, API, tools] --> APM[APM Eclipse plugin] subgraph APM_Box [APM Eclipse plugin] APM_DQ[APM Dynamic Querying] APM_DS[APM Data Services] end APM_Box --> ENACT[ENACT Components] subgraph ENACT_Box [ENACT Components] OR[Orchestrator] TD[Telemetry data collector] DAS[Data access & sharing interfaces] end </pre>

Interfaces	APM Data Services API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
	APM Dynamic Querying API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
	APM Abstraction Layer API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON or YAML or Markup Language
Deployment Type	Docker Containers

Table 11: Application Programming Model Specifications Overview

6.4.2.4 Software Development Kit (SDK)

Component Name	Software Development Kit
Intro / Overview	The SDK provides developers with a development environment, software development tools, libraries, and documentation to develop and integrate applications within the ENACT ecosystem. It facilitates the development of portable apps capable of distributed management of data by mobile devices.
Component Workflow	The component consists of the following modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SDK Libraries provides essential libraries for building ENACT-compatible applications. Development Environment and Tools include tools for coding, debugging, and testing. Documentation offers comprehensive guides and API documentation. Sample Applications demonstrates best practices and common UCs.
Interfaces	SDK Libraries API: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: Provides essential functions and methods for application development. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON Development Tools API: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: Offers tools for debugging and testing applications. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON Documentation API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: Access to guides and API documentation. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: HTML or DOCX or MD

Deployment Type Software

Table 12: SDK Specifications Overview

6.4.2.5 AI Act Compliance Check

Component Name	AI Act Compliance Check
Intro / Overview	<p>The AI compliance check module is designed to automatically verify and ensure that the developed application adheres to the provisions of the AI Act, as well as potentially other relevant legislation and policies. It utilizes meta information provided by the application along with user manuals, descriptions, and other pertinent documents to perform tasks such as categorizing the application from the perspective of the AI Act, evaluating the completeness and quality of the provided documentation, and offering recommendations for necessary changes.</p> <p>AI Act compliance check module consist of two modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Compliance Logic represents the main method, checking compliance of the solution with the AI Act, leveraging data submitted by the application and the Knowledge base. The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant meta data, and provide assessment from the compliance with the AI Act perspective. • The AI Act Knowledge Base in the form of AI model/LLM and supporting RAG features, trained for analysis of the AI Act. The module has to be able to provide/generate answers to questions about the AI act, to assess compliance of an application and, potentially, provide suggestions on how to fix potential issues. <p>Through the interaction with the AC component, Compliance check component will obtain access to the representative data used for training the AI model to assess it from the AI Act perspective as well as make it available in the AI training data sets data space.</p>
Component Workflow	<pre> graph TD subgraph AIActComplianceChecker [AI Act compliance checker] CL[Compliance Logic] <-.-> AIKB[AIAct KnowledgeBase] end AC[Application Controller] <--> CL subgraph ENACTApplicationDevelopmentLayer [ENACT Application Development Layer] AC end </pre>
Interfaces	<p>Score API Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This API will accept content information (metadata, content, additional details) as input and return a determination of whether the content aligns with the AI Act requirements. <p>Update knowledge database Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This API will recreate a knowledge database based on newly uploaded documents.

- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

Dockerised software modules with defined APIs for consumption of provided services. Expected to have two distinct docker containers, one for the logic and another for the knowledge base/AI/LLM model.

Table 13: AI Act Compliance Check Specifications Overview

6.5 Data Layer

6.5.1 Overview

The Data Layer serves as the foundation for data management and access across the entire system. It aims to provide a comprehensive Distributed Data and Object Space across the CCC, promoting secure cross-organisation data sharing while adhering to data sovereignty principles.

The Data Layer interacts with the application development layer, orchestration layer, and VTE component within the ENACT system, by dealing with all data requests, including the proper training datasets for AI models, health logs, alerts, and access tokens, ensuring secure and efficient data sharing across the layers.

Figure 16: ENACT Data Layer Interactions

6.5.2 Data Layer Key Components

6.5.2.1 Data Access & Sharing Interfaces

Component Name	Data Access and Sharing Interfaces
Intro / Overview	The Data Access and Sharing Interfaces will provide mechanisms for accessing and retrieving data stored in the distributed data sources. They include data connectors and APIs, to enable other components and applications to interact with the distributed data store and perform read and write operations.
Component Workflow	There are no internal interactions; legacy APIs and Data Connectors are used for forwarding read/write requests of and transferring data to other ENACT components.

Interfaces

- API Interfaces:**
- Overview: Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- Data Connector Interfaces:**
- Overview: Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components
 - Type: Eclipse Dataspace Protocol
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type Software

Table 14: Data Access & Sharing Interfaces Specifications Overview

6.5.2.2 Data Manager

Component Name	Data Manager
Intro / Overview	The ENACT Data Manager comprises a set of subcomponents to support distributed data storage across the entire computing continuum, metadata management, including indexing/de-indexing and filtering of data, authentication and authorisation mechanisms, as well as monitoring services to keep track of the Distributed Data Storage performance, monitor its health and provide associate alerts and diagnostics.

Data Layer (Space)

Component Workflow

Interfaces
Data Store Interfaces:

- Overview: Used for the execution of CRUD operations
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Metadata Manager Interfaces:

- Overview: Used for the execution of data/metadata write operations
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Security & Access Control Manager Interfaces:

- Overview: Used for handling the authentication and access requests, and forwarding of CRUD requests
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Monitoring Services Interfaces:

- Overview: Used for the execution of health logs read requests
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type

Software – Containerisation approach will be used for the packaging and deployment of various components of ENACT Data Store/Space.

Table 15: Data Manager Specifications Overview

6.6 Virtual Training Environment Component (VTE)

As a central point for the training and retraining of AI Algorithms and models in the ENACT platform, the VTE is shown in the ENACT Architecture as an independent component, and outside of all ENACT Layers. As shown below in Figure 17, the VTE interacts with two distinct layers in the ENACT platform with those being the AI layer, through interaction with the AI Forecaster components, and the Data Layer, through interaction with the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces component.

Through interaction with the AI Layer, the VTE will receive requests from the AI-Forecaster to train or retrain a new or existing AI model. For the training of new models, the user will be able to select algorithms currently available in the VTE, or upload their own, provided models. Within the request for model training or retraining, the location of the TDC dataset will be specified and a location to store the created or updated model. For both the datasets to be used for training, and storage location of the complete model, the DRL should define a "space" or path within the ENACT Data Layer, from which the VTE can load datasets or store models. It is through this process that the VTE will interact with the ENACT Data Layer where it will communicate directly with the Data Access & Sharing Interface to access datasets and store the model.

Legend: **Components in VTE**
Components interacting with VTE

Figure 17: ENACT Virtual Training Environment Interactions

Component Name	Virtual Training Environment
Intro / Overview	<p>The VTE for training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models is a workbench that helps users without skills in Data Analytics, Data Science, and AI techniques, in training their own AI/ML algorithms. The component is composed of four main modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Model Manager is the entry point to the workbench where any of the algorithms present in the platform can be trained with their respective training/validation datasets. The Model Manager is also the place where all trained modules are listed and can be finally configured prior to their execution in the target system. Within this module, the user can connect to data pipelines for serving the trained models predicting the purpose of the selected model. • The Execution Engine is the module where the real execution of the trained models occurs. This module is based on Kubernetes pods and Docker containers to allow these models to be executed elsewhere. • FL Module implemented on infrastructures or clusters within the CCC. Each cluster performs local training on its data, and the FL module aggregates these local models into a comprehensive global model, ensuring data privacy and efficient training. <p>In addition, a General Module is provided which contains all remaining components that may span across several modules such as the user interface, visualisation and security features.</p>
Component Workflow	<p>To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT VTE, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.</p> <p>Component Workflow:</p>

Model Manager Interface:

- Overview: The Model Manger Interface facilitates communication with Model Manager Module and can execute requests to the Execution Engine. Through the Model Manager Interface, a user can perform CRUD operation on existing models, as well as requesting the execution of particular model. In addition, the interface provides endpoints for the upload of train and test data for model training operations. The Model Manager Interface also supports the configuration of models to allow data ingestion from MQTT and AMQP sources.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Initialisation Interface:

- Overview: This interface is responsible for initializing the FL process by distributing the initial model to the virtual edge nodes. It sets up the necessary environment for each node to begin local training.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Local Training Interface:

- Overview: Facilitates the actual training of ML models on local data available at client devices. It ensures models are trained using appropriate configurations and optimisation techniques.
- Type: REST API
- State: Asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Model Aggregation and Update Interface:

- Overview: This interface aggregates the locally trained models from different client devices into a single global model. It ensures that model updates are appropriately weighted and combined.
- Type: REST API

Interfaces

- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Validation and Testing Interface:

- Overview: Validates and tests the aggregated model to ensure it meets specified performance and accuracy criteria. This interface is crucial for certifying the model before deployment.
- Type: REST API
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment and Monitoring Interface:

- Overview: Deploys the validated model to real-world edge devices and cloud servers. This interface also provides continuous monitoring of the model's performance, ensuring it remains effective and efficient in real-world applications.
- Type: REST API
- State: Asynchronous
- Data Format: JSON

- Software as a Service
- Docker Containers

Deployment Type

The current deployment form of the VTE is a series of docker containers. The component is also provided with a docker-compose script that allows for the deployment of all containers in the stack. The component requires minimum resources of 4GB Ram and 2 CPU cores.

Table 16: VTE Specifications Overview

6.7 Cognitive Compute Continuum (CCC) Models

The ENACT CCC Models are a set of data models that facilitate interoperability among other ENACT platform components across the various architecture layers. The CCC Models include three main models:

- The Application / Service Model includes the parameters that can be used for the high-level description of an application to be deployed to the ENACT Continuum, along with its characteristics and the user-set deployment objectives / goals. Based on these parameters, the application deployment can be optimised by the ENACT platform mechanisms. It includes parameters such as the application usage demand, service level (e.g., reliability, accuracy), application performance (e.g., total execution time, response latency, hardware acceleration and its type, parallelisation), data storage and data transfer, network, security and privacy (e.g. encryption, legal framework), energy consumption, deployment cost, timeframe, in-depth technical details (e.g., programming language, execution environment), etc.
- The Resource / Device Model can be utilised for representing the hardware and software resources that will be part of the ENACT Continuum along with their detailed characteristics and attributes. The model is extensible and the entities can be extended to incorporate new hardware types in the future. A hardware resource (Node) can have various attributes (e.g., CPU, Memory, Network, Storage), execution capabilities (e.g., trusted execution enclaves, vector extensions, streaming extensions, software extensions) and one or more attached resources (e.g., GPUs, FPGAs, SmartNICs). A software resource aggregates and handles

multiple hardware resources with different capabilities and offers functional facilities on top (e.g., storage service, execution service).

- The Telemetry Data Model captures the infrastructure runtime measurements of the various resources and components that comprise the ENACT Continuum. Its aim is to adequately describe the state of the hardware and software components available for allocation and usage. It builds on time series streams that refer to the current state of the hardware and low-level software resources available, and covers various telemetry information categories, such as compute, memory, disk, network and hardware. For each of the categories, more in-depth metrics are provided that describe the current state of the infrastructure and enable the ENACT platform components to act on various resources, as required

The CCC Models are utilised by several ENACT components at all architecture layers, as follows:

- In the Modelling Layer, the **DGM**.
- In the Orchestration Layer, the **TDC & Monitoring Engine** and the **Orchestrator**.
- In the AI Layer, the **AI Forecaster**.
- In the Application Development Layer, the **Application Controller, APM, AI Act Compliance Check** and **Application Policy Model**.
- In the Data Layer, the **Data Manager**.
- Finally, in the Physical Layer, the CCC Models could be used directly by various devices connected in the ENACT infrastructure in order to describe their characteristics/capabilities and/or status
- Additionally, the CCC Models are utilised by the API for application deployment (not an ENACT component but still shown in the architecture diagram), which can be used for application deployment, including the specification of the application's characteristics and high-level deployment requirements / goals (e.g., low latency, GDPR-compliance, etc.).

In Figure 18 below, the components that make use of the CCC Models are illustrated in green colour.

Figure 18: Use of CCC Models in ENACT architecture

Table 17 below presents the foreseen associations among the three CCC Models and the ENACT components.

	Application / Service Model	Resource / Device Model	Telemetry Data Model
Modelling Layer			
DGM		✓	✓
Orchestration Layer			
TDC & Monitoring Engine			✓
Orchestrator		✓	✓
AI Layer			
AI Forecaster	✓	✓	✓
Application Development Layer			
Application Controller	✓	✓	✓
APM	✓		
AI Act Compliance Act	✓	✓	✓
Application Policy Model	✓	✓	✓
Data Layer			

Data Manager		√
Physical Layer		
Various devices connected in the ENACT infrastructure	√	√
Other		
API for application development	√	

Table 17: Use of CCC Models in ENACT architecture

Component Name	CCC Models
Intro / Overview	The models provide a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of Service/Application, Resource/Device and Telemetry data, in the context of dynamic heterogeneous complex distributed systems. The models will be used for internal communication of the relevant ENACT components as well as for the definition of high-level Service/Application deployment requirements, the specification of infrastructure Resource/Device characteristics and capabilities, and the collection and storage of Telemetry data for various purposes.
Component Workflow	The CCC Models are not a tangible component, but rather a collection of data models utilised by other ENACT components for interoperability / communication and data storage purposes. As such, no specific workflows can be presented here; however, the CCC Models are utilised in the background within the workflows of other ENACT components and their interactions with each other.
Interfaces	Not applicable.
Deployment Type	Not applicable.

Table 18: CCC Models Specifications Overview

6.8 ENACT Open Collaboration Platform

The section describes the guidelines and infrastructure that the ENACT project has put in place to host its open-source code and to manage its interactions with early adopters, along with supporting open-source best practices such as transparency, openness, meritocracy and vendor neutrality.

6.8.1 Open-Source Governance and the ECLIPSE Development Process

Professional open-source projects are governed according to certain rules, processes and best practices to manage contributions and development by diverse communities. This is especially important for vendor-neutral open-source projects which are not managed by a single entity. The aim for ENACT APM project is to become community-driven, vendor-neutral open-source project.

The Eclipse Development Process defines the processes and rules, governance structures and definitions, project roles, releases and reviews, and interaction between projects and the community².

² <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/>

The very basis for setting up a successful open-source project with proper governance is the project creation. Figure 19 shows the process of project creation at the Eclipse Foundation.

Figure 19: Eclipse project creation process

It starts with a proposal describing the project, the content of the code, the license used, the project leader and the first committers. The proposal is made available to the community for review for two weeks. At the end of the community review period, the creation review begins with a trademark review. After the creation review, the project is created and provisioning can begin, i.e., moving the code to the Eclipse Foundation infrastructure and ensuring that the committer's paperwork is in place (contributor/committer agreements). After the project is provisioned, an Intellectual Property (IP) review is performed to identify potential issues such as missing copyrights, copying code, or incompatible licenses between dependencies or with the license selected by the project. Finally, once the IP review is complete, the initial contribution is released. It can be safely shared with the rest of the world.

The initial contribution when creating a new project consists of a piece of code of various sizes and may belong to a single organisation or different organisations. Contributing a single piece of code, for a single organisation, is straightforward and takes between 2 weeks and 2 months for the creation and the IP review. Conversely, in the case of a large piece of code and/or many contributors from different organisations, which is the case for a research project, this exercise can take a lot of time and effort. In such a context, the Eclipse Foundation has found that this can greatly slow down the project, which is not desirable as the aforementioned task usually occurs in the last few months of the research Project.

Therefore, we have adapted the project creation process to research projects, allowing project partners to get used to open-source best practices and account for the research and development tasks performed during a research project. Eclipse Research Labs aims at gradually and continuously preparing research results to become proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

6.8.2 Implementing Open-Source Best Practices: ENACT Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab³) and trainings to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results. In concrete terms, this means enabling:

- **Open Collaboration:** An open infrastructure (GitLab) has been provided for ENACT consortium to collaborate in the open early, which is one of the main guidelines for doing open source successfully in research projects. It also enables good practices of (open source) software development such as integrating often and soon, automating the process with continuous testing and integration scripts to identify bugs or broken APIs as early as possible.
- **Transparency:** It encourages the consortium to work openly: realising that the code is in the middle of hundreds of millions of public repositories and may go unnoticed, expressing the development plan clearly and openly throughout the process and expressing your decisions clearly and transparently, avoiding drowning them in internal emails. It also eases the communication of early project results to external stakeholders.
- **Community Governance:** Contributor Agreements allow to identify and list the contributors to the open-source project(s) from the beginning. Signing the Eclipse Contributor Agreement (ECA) is a prerequisite for pushing code in one of the ENACT Research Labs repositories. Further information on why an ECA is required and what it is for can be found in the ECA FAQ.
- **Open-Source Licences:** It is important to select appropriate licences for the ENACT outputs, depending on the intended means of exploitation. In the “default cases” this will be EPL-2.0, Apache-2.0 or MIT. As all ENACT results should be commercially exploitable, GPL and similar strong copyleft licences will be avoided.
- **IP Review:** IP reviews help to analyse shared code as early and often as possible to identify potential intellectual property issues, such as missing copyright headers in source files, metadata files in repositories or third-party dependencies with incompatible licences (alternative compatible libraries can be used).

The Eclipse Research Labs GitLab is hosted by OVH and is in France; it is important for the Eclipse Foundation, located in Europe, and for a European research project to be hosted and managed in Europe, following the European laws on privacy and data protection.

Implementing these best practices will allow the project partners to work in a professional open-source environment - based on proven Eclipse Foundation practices – and ease the transition from research results into proper Eclipse Foundation open-source projects. Furthermore, this approach gives the consortium the room to experiment and define the scope of the resulting open-source projects. This approach is depicted in the next figure and is usually realised in three phases.

³ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs>

Figure 20: Eclipse Research Labs Phases

- Phase 1:** Identification of code to open source (M1 – M12). The ENACT consortium selects the parts of the ENACT architecture that are going to be open source. These parts are immediately moved to the Eclipse Research Labs. Additional open-source components can be moved to Research Labs, while any ENACT component may be created directly in the Eclipse Research Labs if it is intended to be open source.
- Phase 2:** Open collaboration development (M7 – M36). During this phase research and development takes place and we ensure the implementation of the aforementioned open-source best practices and governance principles (transparency, openness, IP-analyses, contributor agreements, etc.).
- Phase 3:** Eclipse project creation (M24 – beyond project). When the consortium decides to release a component (or a set thereof) as a vendor-neutral open-source project, the process of moving the project to become a “real” Eclipse Foundation project can be kicked off (as described in section 7.1). Thanks to the Research Labs approach, the necessary open-source good practices are already in place, so this step will in most cases be very smooth.

To facilitate the open-source work to the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, two training sessions will be provided to the consortium:

- Open-Source Ecosystem.
- Open-Source Licensing and Compliance.

The ENACT Research Labs is available to the public⁴.

7. Application of the ENACT Architecture in the Involved Pilots

To highlight the cognitive capabilities of the secure, adaptive and distributed ENACT platform in supporting highly-demanding, dynamic and safety-critical applications, the project will demonstrate two high impact UCs across different domains with heterogeneous needs.

⁴ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project>

7.1 Use Case #1: Distributed Media and Entertainment Content Management

This pilot focuses on adapting a video processing pipeline for automated analysis of live sports broadcasting. Through advanced AI algorithms to process and annotate large quantities of media data from various sources in real-time, this solution focuses on streamline production workflows, making it easier to manage and deliver high-quality sports content. By automatically identifying and tagging key events, players, and other critical elements during live sports broadcasts, this pilot ensures a more efficient and enriched viewing experience for audiences.

Figure 21: MOG's Use Case High-level Architecture

Taking this into account, the CCC architecture, proposed by ENACT, makes it possible to aspire to a new dimension for the pilot's solution by achieving the proposed objectives, which are based on:

1. The seamless integration of edge and cloud resources to **minimize latency**: In live streaming, especially for sports events, minimising latency is crucial to providing viewers with a real-time experience. Edge computing brings processing power closer to the end-user, reducing the time it takes for data to travel between the source (e.g., sports venue camera's) and the viewer's device. By processing and delivering content at the network edge, latency can be significantly reduced, enhancing the viewing experience;
2. The use of diverse devices to reach **scalability, optimize processing and storage capacities**: Sports events, especially major tournaments or matches, can attract millions of viewers simultaneously and, therefore, are covered by several cameras. Cloud computing provides scalability, allowing streaming platforms with automatic computer vision analysis to dynamically allocate resources based on demand. Additionally, edge computing can offload processing tasks from centralised data centres to edge nodes, further enhancing scalability
3. Automatic load-balancing and application elasticity to meet varying demand patterns, which lead to an **enhanced Quality of Service (QoS)**: The computing continuum allows for intelligent resource allocation and traffic management, leading to improved QoS for live streaming;
4. **Dynamic adaptation to accommodate changes** in infrastructure or user behaviour: Distributed computing architectures, such as edge and fog computing, **enhance the reliability and resilience** of live streaming systems. By decentralising processing and storage capabilities across multiple edge nodes, these architectures reduce single points of failure and improve fault tolerance. In the event of network disruptions or server failures, edge

computing ensures continuity of service by seamlessly redirecting traffic to alternate nodes, thereby enhancing overall system reliability.

Overall, a CCC offers compelling motivations for leveraging its capabilities in live streaming, particularly for sports content where real-time delivery, scalability, and quality are paramount. By harnessing edge and cloud computing technologies, streaming platforms can deliver immersive, high-quality viewing experiences to sports fans worldwide. This expected result aligns with market needs and tenders, fulfilling MOG's key motivation.

These benefits are connected to ENACT's architecture. The DGM and according connection to the AI Layer permits a dynamic understanding of the infrastructure capable of providing the best possible infrastructure scenario for this UC deployment according to the current status and from previous deployment based on RL techniques. To deploy the application components, the user will submit a request to ENACT's Orchestrator specifying the required resources (e.g., minimum CPU, bandwidth, or GPU-equipped devices) and deployment objectives (e.g., resource optimisation, processing speed, or resource consumption). Furthermore, by leveraging ENACT's architecture—continuous communication between the TDC, DGM, Orchestrator, and AI Layer—it is possible to adapt to optimal deployment strategies even in the event of infrastructure degradation enhancing capability the (iv) objective outlined above.

This use case will leverage both Cloud and Edge resources, dynamically distributing workloads based on the current needs and infrastructure status as provided by ENACT. It is specifically tailored for live events, where the infrastructure includes a fixed number of edge devices located near the event venue. The cloud infrastructure remains agnostic, as all components are containerized. Before the event begins, users must be able to register the available infrastructure through the Orchestrator.

In addition to existing telemetry data, certain use case components may expose custom metrics endpoints. This would enable ENACT's TDC and Monitoring Engine to scrape these metrics and produce alerts. The Dynamic Graph Modeller would then provide this data to the AI layer, which would infer the optimal deployment strategies.

7.2 Use Case #2: Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

The goal of this use-case is to develop distributed deployment configurations for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform to enable its execution in a cloud-to-edge continuum.

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform, also known as Dracena (Dynamically Reconfigurable Asynchronous Consistent Event Processing Architecture), is an innovative real-time digital twin platform designed to address the growing needs of the mobility sector. As the automotive industry undergoes a significant transformation towards connected and autonomous vehicles, there is an increasing demand for platforms that can process and analyse vast amounts of real-time data from multiple sources.

Dracena serves as a cloud-based digital twin platform capable of creating virtual representations of people, things, and contexts from the real world. It is specifically engineered to handle large-scale concurrent stream processing, allowing for the real-time analysis and prediction of events in the mobility domain. The platform's architecture is built to process high-frequency data transmitted from millions of devices such as connected cars, smartphones, and various sensors distributed across the transportation infrastructure.

Key features of the Mobility Digital Twin platform include:

1. Real-time data processing: Dracena can manage large volumes of stream data at high speeds, enabling timely decision-making and service delivery;
2. Flexible digital twins: The platform abstracts real-world data in real time, providing flexible representations of mobility-related entities that can be easily adapted for numerous services;
3. Seamless upgrading: Dracena allows for dynamic additions or changes to data processing programs without service interruption, ensuring continuous operation of critical mobility services;
4. Scalability: The platform is designed to scale efficiently, accommodating the growing number of connected vehicles and devices in the mobility ecosystem;
5. Service object architecture: Dracena uses a unique object-oriented approach, separating generic "real-world objects" from service-specific "service objects," allowing for efficient development and event process.

The goal of the use case is to measure the behaviour of the Digital Twin Utilizer (DTU) under various load conditions. Having said that we would like to learn what are the most optimal hardware specs for low, mid, and high load condition and in situation of appearing short high loads. Gathered metrics of infrastructure under of various loads are an essential part of the use case. Data in data layer shall be used for AI and modeler layers for forecasting of hardware utilization. The outcome of AI model will produce the most cost effective and performance effective solution (hardware specs) of the Digital Twin solution.

The Mobility Digital Twin platform leverages containerization technology and cloud infrastructure for its deployment. The platform consists of various microservices, and components packaged as container images, enabling a modular and scalable architecture.

For the purposes of testing and validation within the ENACT project, the chosen deployment environment is Amazon Web Services (AWS) Elastic Kubernetes Service (EKS)⁵. AWS EKS provides a managed Kubernetes cluster, allowing for easy deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications.

Building upon the previous deployment experience, the Mobility Digital Twin platform components will be deployed as Kubernetes 'Stateful Set' objects within the AWS EKS cluster.

Overall, the system can be described as a service with optional plugins that as input takes message queues with data, and the output returns message queues with results.

⁵ <https://aws.amazon.com/eks/>

Figure 22: Digital Twin Utiliser High-level Design

Input data is sourced in IOT/edge computing layer, which is not managed by ENACT. However, ENACT is capable to monitor network traffic from edge devices.

Key components of DTU are Kafka⁶, Apache Flink⁷, Dracena containers, and Data Streaming Analytics Platform. Considering the amount of traffic, requests, etc., are sent to and from DTU measured by orchestration layer modeler, and AI layer can then choose how much resource is needed for DTU components. DTU may use purely Kubernetes as a deployment platform, on-prem/VMs, and mix with managed services like Amazon Managed Streaming for Apache Kafka (MSK)⁸. In this very use case Kubernetes approach with deployed all components as containers is considered as the target.

⁶ <https://kafka.apache.org>

⁷ <https://flink.apache.org>

⁸ <https://aws.amazon.com/msk/>

Figure 23: Digital Twin Utiliser Architecture Design In-depth

Kafka brokers are publicly available and should be scaled accordingly to the load by orchestration layer, requested by AI layer. Second part of scaling is DTU itself, which consists of Apache Flink Dracena containers and HDFS nodes.

Figure 24: Digital Twin Utiliser Deployment Model

Kafka is publicly available, deployed on one Kubernetes cluster. Kafka is using HDFS storage. The second private cluster contains Dracena pods and Apache Flink nodes (masters and slaves). This one also requires HDFS storage.

Orchestration layer may communicate with K8s APIs and AWS API. Data layer will contain all metrics and events related to each node, the modeler and AI layer will learn and request infrastructure changes in both AWS cloud Kubernetes clusters.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the first iteration of ENACT platform's architecture, its main functionalities and interactions, and demonstrating how its multi-layer design and technological innovations will enable the seamless integration of distributed infrastructures across edge, cloud, and physical layers.

The deliverable described the concepts of Resource-level and Application-level Adaptations, the ten (10) innovations that enable these functionalities, the five (5) Layers and seventeen (17) components the CCC consists of and 4 of its main workflows. as well how the ENACT architecture interacts with the physical layers and enables two (2) of the pilot applications. Partners associated with Pilot 3 of the ENACT proposal withdrew in the early stages of the project, and the introduction of a replacement Pilot is currently in process and being finalized which will be included in the final version of the deliverable.

As ENACT continues its development, this document will serve as a guiding framework for further technical work, ensuring that the platform's components and interfaces are aligned with its overarching vision.

The Architecture will be continuously updated and optimized based on real-world pilot deployments (WP3) contributing to the platform's evolution and its ability to meet the diverse demands of its UCs, while also receiving input from the other technical WPs of the project (WP4, WP5 and WP6).

This deliverable will serve as and receive input from T2.1 and its relevant deliverable (D2.1) as the architecture's component specifications evolve until it the architecture and this document is finalized in M18.